

UNIVERSITY OF MEDICINE AND PHARMACY OF CRAIOVA

FACULTY OF MEDICINE

LICENCE THESIS

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATOR,

Professor Dr Vreju Ananu Florentin

ADVISOR,

Lecturer Dr Dinescu Stefan Cristian

GRADUATE:

Ismail Mohammed Sharif Qureshi

CRAIOVA

2023

UNIVERSITY OF MEDICINE AND PHARMACY OF CRAIOVA

FACULTY OF MEDICINE

Biologic and targeted synthetic disease-
modifying anti-rheumatic drugs in rheumatoid
arthritis

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATOR,

Professor Dr Vreju Ananu Florentin

ADVISOR,

Lecturer Dr Dinescu Stefan Cristian

GRADUATE:

Ismail Mohammed Sharif Qureshi

CRAIOVA

2023

I dedicate this thesis to my Mother and Father, without whom I wouldn't be the man I am today; and to Salva Abdollahi, who encourages me to be the man I wish to be in the future

Table of Contents

1. General Part

I. Introduction	3
II. Epidemiology	4
III. Pathogenesis	4
IV. Clinical Features of Rheumatoid Arthritis	6
V. Diagnostic Tests	8
VI. Treatment	12
i. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs)	12
ii. Glucocorticoids	13
iii. csDMARDs	15
iv. tsDMARDs	15
v. bDMARDs (Biologics)	15
vi. Treatment Algorithm	16

2. Special Part

VII. Aim	18
VIII. Methodology	18
IX. Results	21
X. Discussion	37
XI. Conclusions	43
XII. References	44

General Part

I. Introduction:

Rheumatology is the subspecialty of internal medicine often charged with the diagnosis and treatment of conditions affecting the musculoskeletal system. The term itself originates from the Greek word 'rheuma' meaning that which 'flows as a river or stream'. The British Society of Rheumatology defines this specialty as a 'multidisciplinary branch of medicine that deals with the investigation, diagnosis and management of patients with arthritis and other musculoskeletal conditions...incorporating over 200 disorders affecting joints, bones, muscles and soft tissues, including inflammatory arthritis and other systemic autoimmune disorders' (Wilkinson et al. 2017, p. 538).

Musculoskeletal pain is the most common presenting symptom to the rheumatologist which comprises of 25-30% of consultations in primary care (Kumar and Clark 2021, p. 411), it is entirely subjective in its description and may vary depending on physical and biological factors. Pain is often the most presenting complaint and the experience is different for every individual. It may be localised or caused by a distant lesion. Certain rheumatological conditions are prone to patterns of pain distribution and can be identified based on the cluster of symptoms (with or without laboratory workup).

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic systemic autoimmune disease of unknown aetiology which mainly targets smaller synovial joints causing symmetrical joint synovitis. The synovial tissues proliferate — which causes bony destruction, deformity, and disability. This is mainly due to the stretching of ligaments and tendons which leads to inflammation of the synovial membrane. Symmetrical, deforming, and peripheral polyarthritis is characteristic of RA. Typically the small joints of the hands and feet are affected, although any synovial joint can be affected. Synovitis often presents with pain and prolonged stiffness that tends to be worse on rest or after periods of inactivity, tenderness, swelling, and heat in the affected joints. Other symptoms of rheumatoid arthritis include rheumatoid nodules as well as non-specific symptoms such as fever, fatigue, malaise, and weight loss. RA can lead to predisposition of cardiovascular comorbidity (increasing the risk by 2-3 fold) and increased susceptibility to infectious pathogens, these can combine to reduce life expectancy by up to 10 years in severe cases (Watts et al. 2013, p. 839; Wilkinson et al. 2017, p. 546).

The aim of this thesis project will focus primarily on rheumatoid arthritis and its treatment with a focus on targeted synthetic and biologic disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs).

II. Epidemiology:

Rheumatoid Arthritis cases around the world differ in distribution, some sources claim that 0.5-1% of the population are affected with a 3:1 female to male ratio (Kumar and Clark 2021, p.437), and others would add that while women have an increased incidence of RA until roughly the age of 50 where it plateaus; RA in adult males before the age of 40 is uncommon but the incidence increases steadily with age (O'Dell et al. 2013, p. 42). Presentation in early childhood is rare but new-onset RA is common in late to old age with men and women in the seventh to ninth decade of life. In the United Kingdom the rates are 1.5-3.6 per 10,000 people per year, with the ratio of 3:1 in favour of women remaining the same (Clunie et al. 2018, p. 282).

First-degree relatives of patients with RA have an increased risk of developing the disease, with siblings of severely affected patients being at the highest risk. Monozygotic twins have a 12-15% concordance but dizygotic twins only have a 3% concordance rate (Cava and Albani 1998, p. 2111).

III. Pathogenesis:

Since rheumatoid arthritis is an inflammatory disease, it manifests primarily in the synovial tissues (although the reason why this occurs is still unknown) leading to a dysregulation of the inflammatory cascade due to interactions between T lymphocytes, B lymphocytes, and synovial fibroblasts leading to chronic inflammation.

A normal synovium comprises of a thin layer of fibroblast-like synoviocytes and macrophages; they overlie the loose connective tissue, but in RA the synovium becomes increasingly thickened which leads to swelling of the joints and tendons and proliferation of the synovium, with infiltration of inflammatory cells moving from the tissue into the joint fluid, lymphocytes, and plasma cells. The normally sparse surface layer of lining cells becomes thickened and hyperplastic with increased vascular proliferation, permeable blood vessels, and synovial lining layer — which lead to joint effusions. This hyperplastic synovium spreads from the joint margins to the cartilage surface and this damages the underlying cartilage, since normal routes of nutrition are blocked and cytokines as well as chondrocytes directly effect the layers thinning them down until the bone is exposed. Cytokine production and disused joints (due to the pain) combine together to cause juxta-articular osteoporosis, increased bone resorption activates osteoclasts which erode the bones. Due to this proliferating synovium, fibroblasts grow along the trajectory of the blood vessels, between the epiphyseal bone cavity and synovial margins; this leads to bone damage, erosions, and a variety of deformities which can lead to long-term disability.

An overproduction of inflammatory cytokines such as tumour necrosis factor- α (TNF α) and interleukin-6 (IL-6) is key to the pathology of RA. The interaction of macrophages and T and B lymphocytes is the driving force behind the overproduction of TNF α which in turn stimulates production of IL-6 and other cytokines. Increased inflammation leads to hypervascularisation and synovitis (inflammation of the synovial lining of joints), cartilage degradation (which leads to joint space narrowing), and bone erosion in extreme cases if the inflammation is persistent.

Serum autoantibody studies can be done to more accurately confirm the diagnosis of RA. Rheumatoid factor (RF) is detected by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). RF can be of any immunoglobulin class (IgG, IgM, or IgA) but standardised tests for RA look for IgM RF. Whilst seronegative RA does occur (tests for IgM RF showing up negative), it is not diagnostic for RA as it is only in roughly 70% of cases of RA, and its absence does not necessarily rule out the disease as it can also be present in other rheumatological diseases such as systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) and in chronic infections (Kumar and Clark 2021, p. 416-437). In early RA a high titre may indicate a more persistently active synovitis which leads to more joint damage and disability.

Synovial B cells are activated by cytokines, macrophages, and T cells; they produce autoantibodies of which IgM RF is most typical in RA. Once the RF binds to IgG Fc receptors they self-aggregate and form an immune complex in the synovial membranes. This in turn triggers macrophages to produce even more cytokines such as IL-1, IL-8, and TNF- α to produce IL-6 which leads to inflammation. T cells are a part of the destructive process also. The pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-17 is produced by specific T-helper cells to produce IL-17, 21 and 22, and TNF- α . Normal regulatory T cells are suppressed by TGF- β and interleukins (they are produced by dendritic and macrophage cells), this then causes more T-helper cells to increase in number and therefore more inflammatory cytokines produced.

Anti-citrullinated peptide antibodies (ACPA) are antibodies directed against citrullinated antigens (citrulline-modified autoantigens) (Watts et al. 2013, p. 840). They are measured by an ELISA technique and are present in up to 80% of people with RA with a high specificity of 95% and sensitivity of 67%; compared to RF specificity and sensitivity of 85% and 69% respectively (Nishimura et al. 2007, p. 797-808). They are helpful in early disease diagnosis when the RF is negative. Positive RF and/or ACPA is associated with a worse prognosis and increases the likelihood of bony erosions. Patients may begin to produce high levels of antibodies to CCP which is specific to RA while rheumatoid factor (RF) is non-specific.

Genetics also contribute to the risk of developing RA, genetic marker HLA-DR4 'shared epitope' (a common amino acid sequence found in the hyper-variable regions of certain HLA-DR alleles) is a human leukocyte antigen which is an anomaly found present in white

blood cells which increases the risk for RA development; HLA is used to distinguish the body's own cells from foreign invaders but due to an anomaly HLA-DR4 is unable to differentiate foreign and self-cells and attacks the body (Hou, Xu and Wang 2011, p. 94). An increase in HLA-DR4/DR1 leads to an increase in severity of RA (Wilkinson et al. 2017, p. 546). This is one of the most strongly associated genetic factors for RA.

Smoking can also lead to an increased risk of RA due to bronchial stress and mucosal site damage with HLA-DR4 increasing and HLA-DRB1 acting synergistically with ACPA, this reflects autoimmunity towards a group of citrulline-modified autoantigens, this citrullination of proteins is more likely in cellular inflammation, stress, and autophagy (Kumar and Clark 2021, p. 437). Smoking contributes approximately 25% of the risk of RA (Watts et al. 2013, p. 841).

Environmental or genetic interactions promote citrullination of self proteins, which is then detected by T and B cells. This leads to a loss of tolerance and produces the inflammatory response which results in joint damage.

IV. Clinical features of rheumatoid arthritis:

Onset of rheumatoid arthritis is characterised by progressive, symmetrical, and peripheral polyarthritis primarily affecting the metacarpal-phalangeal (MCP), proximal interphalangeal (PIP), and metatarso-phalangeal (MTP) joints. The distal inter-phalangeal (DIP) joints are most often spared. Although RA mainly affects the small joints of the hands and feet; any joint, bursa, or tendon where there is synovial tissue can be affected such as the elbows, shoulders, ankles, knees, and hips. Joint symptoms develop over weeks but it is not uncommon for symptoms to manifest over a few days. Clinical symptoms can be split into multiple categories such as articular (joints and tendons), extra-articular, and systemic.

Articular symptoms often start in the small joints of the hands and feet with soft tissue swelling secondary to effusions. If the effusions persist then the tendons and ligaments are stretched and deformed. Stiffness worse in the morning and lasting for more than 30 minutes is also characteristic of RA, comparing that with stiffness being worse in the evening for osteoarthritis. Joint symptoms can develop over a few weeks and normally follow a specific order of disease progression. Early disease affects the MCPs, PIPs, and MTPs; intermediate affects the wrists, knees, elbows, and ankles; late involves the hips, shoulders, and C1 (Atlas) C2 (Axis) articulation (atlanto-axial subluxation may threaten the spinal cord but is rare). In the early stages the fingers will be swollen, stiff, and painful but movement of the affected joint can alleviate stiffness and discomfort. Deformities can include radio-ulnar deviation at the wrist which can be accompanied by a depressible prominent ulnar styloid due to instability and dorsal subluxation of the ulnar head, this is called the piano-key phenomenon. In advanced disease progression Swan-neck

(hyperextension at PIP joint and hyperflexion at DIP joint) and Boutonniere or 'button-hole' (hyperflexion at PIP joint and hyperextension at DIP joint) deformities can be seen in the fingers (Darby, Barron and Hyland 2012, p. 268). Subluxation of the metatarsal heads can lead to discomfort when walking. Ankylosis of the carpal bones can also be seen on plain film X-ray imaging. Limited shoulder movement due to ligament rupture, joint erosion, or effusion can be seen in intermediate progression.

Extra-articular symptoms can manifest and play a significant role in treatment decisions and prognosis, they can affect up to 40% of patients (Wilkinson et al. 2017, p. 546). Rheumatoid nodules are subcutaneous nodules that present in seropositive patients (RF or ACPA) and can occur anywhere in the body but are mostly found on the hands, elbows, and feet; they generally occur over pressure points. Tenosynovitis of the flexor tendons of the hand can cause stiffness and occasionally a trigger finger as well as swelling of the extensor tendon sheath on the dorsum of the hand. In the lungs pulmonary fibrosis, exudative pleural effusions, pleurisy, interstitial lung disease and bronchiectasis can occur which can lead to respiratory distress due to the accumulating pleural fluid. Cardiac manifestations include coronary artery disease and atherosclerosis especially if RA is poorly controlled and the patient has increased C-reactive protein (CRP) and hypercholesterolaemia which are cardiovascular risk factors. Pericarditis and endocarditis can also occur though they are rarely asymptomatic, along with pericardial effusion and ischaemic heart disease. The eyes can develop scleritis and episcleritis in severe seropositive RA which can cause painful red eye and must be considered an emergency situation due to the risk of progression into eye perforation resulting in blindness. Secondary Sjögren's syndrome occurs in roughly 25% of patients and is characterised by typical sicca symptoms of the eye and mouth.

Regarding systemic symptoms: RA may manifest with fatigue, anaemia, and weight loss; which are prominent symptoms that are difficult to manage (in regard to fatigue). Systemic inflammation in RA damages blood vessels and can lead to premature atherosclerosis. Haematological effects can include anaemia of chronic disease, thrombocytosis (which parallels inflammation), and Felty's syndrome (which is the triad of leukopaenia, splenomegaly, and RA). Osteoporosis is increased approximately twofold in males and females in RA, generalised bone loss being well documented. Due to the resultant bone loss there may be an increased risk of vertebral or non-vertebral fractures (especially in the pelvis, hip, tibia, fibula, and humerus). This is driven by the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL6 which impacts bone metabolism; immobilisation can also occur due to functional impairment and pain. Osteoporosis is more common than in the general population due to steroids, reduced mobility, and systemic inflammation. Periodontitis and tooth loss are also common in RA (de Pablo et al. 2009, p. 218-224).

Due to the inflammatory nature of RA various markers can be a sign of disease activity, albeit some are non-specific and can be an indication of infection, obesity (in the case for

CRP), or malignancy. RA is usually associated with an acute phase response, with erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and C-reactive protein (CRP) being the more commonly used markers for inflammation. ESR measures how quickly red blood cells fall in a column in 1 hour, however, raised ESR levels don't necessarily mean raised levels of inflammation, especially since ESR levels tend to increase with age (Provan 2018, p. 744). CRP is driven by IL-1 and IL-6 on hepatocytes and generally provides a more accurate reflection of inflammatory processes than ESR, since it changes rapidly and is independent of variables that complicate ESR interpretation, it is generally 100 times more sensitive than ESR. In cases where ESR/CRP are increased in active disease, they are extremely useful in monitoring disease activity in response to treatment (Provan 2018, p. 744). Figure 1 below shows how ESR and CRP can be used in rheumatological diagnoses.

Diagnosis	ESR	CRP
Infection	↑↑ or ↑↑↑	↑↑ or ↑↑↑
Malignancy	Normal to ↑↑	Normal to ↑
RhA	↑↑	↑↑
SLE*	↑	Normal to ↑
SLE with serositis	↑	Normal to ↑↑
Gout/ CPPD**	↑↑ or ↑↑↑	↑↑ or ↑↑↑
Sjögren's syndrome	↑ or ↑↑	↑
Vasculitis	↑↑ or ↑↑↑	↑↑ or ↑↑↑
Osteoarthritis	Normal	Normal
Psoriatic arthritis/spondyloarthropathy	Normal to ↑↑	Normal to ↑↑

* Systemic lupus erythematosus.
 ** Calcium pyrophosphate disease.

(Figure 1) ESR and CRP in diagnosis (Provan 2018, p. 745)

V. Diagnostic tests, criteria:

RA is primarily a clinical diagnosis. However, a baseline set of investigations must be performed to assist in the diagnosis. Laboratory tests and imaging are key to help provide a point of reference for monitoring disease progression, drug response, and toxicity. Some individuals may not fall into specific diagnostic groups and thus are described as having an undifferentiated peripheral inflammatory arthritis (UPIA), but defining UPIA is difficult

and the classification is broad, since it is a dynamic condition. Only by making a thorough evaluation and excluding other diagnoses can this condition be omitted, see Figure 2 below.

The American College of Rheumatology (ACR) stated that at least 4 of the following criteria, lasting up to 6 weeks, are required for diagnosis of RA: early morning joint stiffness for more than 1 hour before improvement; simultaneous swelling in at least 3 joints; symmetrical arthritis involving the proximal interphalangeal (PIP) joints, metacarpophalangeal (MCP) joints, or the wrist; subcutaneous nodules; positive rheumatoid factor above the 95th percentile; and typical radiological findings of erosions and peri-articular osteopaenia (Arnett et al. 1988, p. 315-324).

A revised classification criteria was devised in 2010 in a joint effort between ACR and the European League Against Rheumatism (EULAR) which replaced the 1987 criteria (Aletaha et al. 2008). The criteria is made up of 4 domains (a score of $>6/10$ is required for a definite classification of a patient with RA): Joint involvement (1 large joint = 0, 2-10 large joints = 1, 1-3 small joints = 2, 4-10 small joints = 3, >10 joints including one small joint = 4), serology (at least one is required for classification; negative RF *AND* negative ACPA = 0, low positive RF *OR* low positive ACPA = 2, high positive RF *OR* high positive ACPA = 3), acute phase reactants (at least one is required for classification; normal CRP *AND* normal ESR = 0, abnormal CRP *OR* abnormal ESR = 1), and duration of symptoms (<6 weeks = 0, ≥ 6 weeks = 1), see Figure 3 below for outline.

The most commonly used indicator for RA disease activity and response to treatment is the Disease Activity Score of 28 joints (DAS28) (Prevo et al. 1995, p. 44-48). The DAS28 scores range from 0 to 9.4 and are calculated using tender joints, swollen joints, general health, and a laboratory measure of acute inflammation which can be erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) or C-reactive protein (CRP) (Greenmyer et al. 2020, p. 2). Figure 4 below shows an example of the joints included in the DAS28 and the form used for recording disease activity at the Royal Derby Hospital (United Kingdom). This consists of a tender joint count, swollen joint count, measure of inflammation (ESR or CRP), and a visual analogue of global health (1-100) (Watts et al. 2013, p. 870). A DAS28 score of greater than 5.1 implies active disease, less than 3.2 low disease activity and less than 2.6 remission (Kumar and Clark 2021, p. 444).

(Figure 2) Algorithm for identification of UPIA. *Recommended minimum investigations in all patients: rheumatoid factor and/or anticitrullinated peptide antibodies, erythrocyte sedimentation rate and/or C-reactive protein, complete blood count, and radiographs of affected joints. Radiographs of hands, wrists, and feet should be considered, particularly if rheumatoid arthritis is a diagnostic consideration. P/E: physical examination; DDX: differential diagnosis, SpA: spondyloarthritis; UPIA: undifferentiated peripheral inflammatory arthritis (Hazlewood et al. 2011, p. 54-58).

Criteria	Points
1. Joint involvement	0–5
1 medium to large joint	0
2–10 medium to large joints	1
1–3 small joints (large joints not counted)	2
4–10 small joints (large joints not counted)	3
>10 joints; at least one small joint	5
2. Serology	0–3
Negative RF and negative ACPA	0
Low positive RF or low positive ACPA	2
High positive RF or high positive ACPA	3
3. Acute-phase reactants	0–1
Normal CRP and normal ESR	0
Abnormal CRP or abnormal ESR	1
4. Duration of symptoms	0–1
<6 weeks	0
≥6 weeks	1

(Figure 3) ACR/EULAR 2010 criteria for rheumatoid arthritis (Kumar and Clark 2021, p. 440)

^aThe cut-off point for RA is at ≥6 points. Patients can also be classified as having RA if they have both typical erosions and longstanding disease previously satisfying the classification criteria. ACPA, anticitrullinated peptide antibody; ACR, American College of Rheumatology; CRP, C-reactive protein; EULAR, European League Against Rh. (Adapted from Scott DL, Wolfe F, Huizinga TW. Rheumatoid arthritis. Lancet 2010; 376:1094–1108.)

Which joints are **tender**? (please tick)

Which joints are **swollen**? (please tick)

Global VAS: Overall well being: Please indicate on the scale below

0 100

Best Imaginable Health State Worst Imaginable Health State

NAME: _____ DATE: _____

METHODS: _____

CHANGES IN PAST 6 MONTHS: _____

ADMISSIONS: _____

ESR:

CRP:

WEIGHT: _____

PREDNISILONE DOSE: _____

INFECTIONS/ADVERSE EVENTS NEW ILLNESS: _____

(Figure 4) DAS28 Scoring System (Watts et al. 2013, p. 870)

VI. Treatment:

While there is currently no cure for RA, or in fact any of the rheumatological diseases, there do exist drugs that can treat the underlying cause of the disease via various mechanisms. It is due to the understanding of these mechanisms which has informed the development of targeted biological and synthetic therapies to help combat the disease, such drugs are named disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs).

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs)

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are generally used by patients with RA to relieve night pain and morning stiffness, in addition with other medications which we will explain further on. NSAIDs, as with all drugs, are not without their side effects and it depends on the type of drug used and its mechanism. NSAIDs work on the principal of cyclooxygenase enzyme (COX) inhibition by stopping arachidonic acid oxidation by the COX enzymes. The two common isoforms of COX are COX-1 and COX-2, they are closely related and catalyse the same reaction but have important differences and roles. COX-1 is an enzyme that is expressed in most tissues such as blood platelets and has a general 'housekeeping' role in the body. It is primarily involved in tissue homeostasis and responsible for producing prostaglandins which are involved in gastric protection, platelet aggregation, and renal blood flow regulation (and others). COX-2 is induced in inflammatory cells when they are injured, infected or activated by, for example, the inflammatory cytokines—interleukin (IL)-1 and tumour necrosis factor (TNF)- α (Rang et al. 2012, p. 318). COX-2 is the isoform mainly responsible for the production of inflammatory mediators. Most NSAIDs traditionally inhibit both COX-1 and COX-2 in different degrees, some are selective (only one or the other) and some are non-selective (weakly towards one and the other). It is believed that the anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties of NSAIDs are related to COX-2 inhibition, whereas the unwanted side effects such as gastrointestinal issues are largely the effect of COX-1 inhibition. For example aspirin is weakly COX-1 selective which explains the gastrointestinal side effects and platelet anti-aggregation effects. Diclofenac on the other hand is weakly COX-2 selective and doesn't have the COX-1 side effects like aspirin and ibuprofen do (Rang et al. 2012, p. 319).

Glucocorticoids

Glucocorticoids are corticosteroids that also have anti-inflammatory properties. They were the first pharmacologic agents used as immunosuppressives in both transplantation and various autoimmune disorders. Steroids have a greater potency than NSAIDs because they

act on numerous inflammatory pathways, and not just antagonising COX. They are also disease-modifying, unlike NSAIDs, and are relatively safe when compared to the contraindications of NSAIDs such as ischaemic heart disease, asthma, and renal disease (Watts et al. 2013, p. 871). Steroids can be injected directly into inflamed joints for localised pain relief directly at the source, or given as an intramuscular injection. Of course, like all medications, they aren't without side effects which need to be carefully monitored. Adverse effects such as hyperglycaemia, insulin resistance, osteoporosis, glaucoma, and various cardiovascular and metabolic effects including suppression of the immune system leaving the patient susceptible to infections.

Disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs)

While NSAIDs are primarily used for pain relief and reduction in symptoms such as inflammation; they have minimal, if any, effects on progression of the disease. This is where DMARDs come in and either halt or retard the progression of the disease using varying mechanisms. DMARDs are a heterogeneous group of drugs with vastly unrelated chemical structures and mechanisms of action. DMARDs include a diverse group of small molecular non-biological and biological agents. For the sake of this thesis, and when trying to better differentiate the classes (and for ease of understanding), we shall classify the drugs as such:

csDMARDs (conventional synthetic DMARDs) such as Methotrexate (MTX), Leflunomide (LEF), Hydroxychloroquine (HCQ), Sulfasalazine (SSZ), Cyclosporine, Azathioprine, and Auranofin

bDMARDs or biologics (biological DMARDs) such as Adalimumab, Golimumab, Etanercept, Infliximab, Certolizumab, Abatacept, Rituximab, Anakinra, Tocilizumab, and Tofacitinib (Gilman, Alfred Goodman 2018, p. 702)

tsDMARDs (targeted synthetic DMARDs) such as Baricitinib, Filgotinib, and Tofacitinib. These tend to be known as Janus Kinase inhibitors or JAK inhibitors

Conventional synthetic disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (csDMARDs)

csDMARDs are slow-acting drugs that take 8-12 weeks to begin to show a demonstrable benefit, and possibly even longer to achieve maximum efficacy which is typically >6 months. It is not uncommon to combine multiple csDMARDs for maximum efficacy in either a step-up (adding one after the other over time) or step-down (starting with two or three then removing one after the other over time until one remains) drug regime (Clunie et al. 2018, p. 688).

Examples of csDMARDs are:

- **Methotrexate (MTX)** - A folic acid antagonist with immunosuppressant and cytotoxic properties. It is often the first-line drug given due to its potent anti-rheumatoid properties and it has a quicker onset of action compared to other DMARDs. Due to its potential to cause unwanted side effects such as blood dyscrasias and liver cirrhosis close monitoring is highly recommended. Even with the aforementioned side effects MTX is superior to other DMARDs in part due to its efficacy and unwanted effects, and is often given in combination with other DMARDs (Rang et al. 2012, p. 327). It is recommended that folic acid supplements are given when taking MTX. As with most antimetabolites, it is only partially selective and can kill rapidly dividing normal cells as well, this explains the mucosal ulceration and nausea that patients can sometimes feel.
- **Leflunomide (LEF)** - An immunomodulatory agent that causes cell inhibition of activated T cells. It not only reduces pain and inflammation associated with the disease but also appears to slow the progression of structural damage (Harvey et al. 2009, p. 511). LEF is orally active and well absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract along with having a long plasma half-life and the active metabolite undergoes entero-hepatic circulation. The side effects can include diarrhoea, alopecia, raised liver enzymes, and a risk of hepatic failure.
- **Hydroxychloroquine (HCQ)** - An older generation anti-malarial that has anti-rheumatic effects but doesn't appear until after 1 month or more once the drug is started and only about 50% of patients respond to treatment (Rang et al. 2012, p. 328). It is often used for early, mild RA and has relatively few side effects. It is often combined with other DMARDs such as MTX to help slow down joint damage.
- **Sulfasalazine (SSZ)** - Classed as a salicylate and sulfonamide, it is split into its constituent parts in the colon by bacteria. Like with other salicylates, SSZ has NSAID-like properties but also the side effects associated with them; gastrointestinal disturbances, peptic lesions, interstitial nephritis, and tinnitus. Other side effects of SSZ include headache, skin reactions, leukopaenia, and decrease in sperm count in males. These effects are reversible once treatment is stopped. It is recommended that haematological monitoring take place when administering SSZ, and due to the impairment of folic acid absorption folic acid supplements can sometimes be given (Rang et al. 2012, p. 328).
- **Ciclosporin/cyclosporine** - A naturally occurring compound first found in fungus, it is an immunosuppressant drug that inhibits IL-2 production and reduces lymphocyte proliferation by acting selectively on the induction phase of the immunological response and blocking mitosis thereby inhibiting lymphokine release. The commonest and most serious unwanted effect of ciclosporin is nephrotoxicity (Rang et al. 2012, p. 329). Care

must be taken when taking this drug when ingesting foods and substances that contain furanocoumarins like grapefruit, as they can interact with CYP3A4 enzymes, which are responsible for metabolising drugs in the body. Grapefruit tends to increase the bioavailability of ciclosporin in the body via CYP3A4. It is also recommended to avoid HCQ as it can increase the plasma concentration of ciclosporin as well.

Targeted synthetic disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (tsDMARDs)

tsDMARDs such as **Tofacitinib** are in a class of their own since they aren't really true biologics but act as such by acting as Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitors, specifically JAK1 and JAK2, which impairs the JAK-STAT signalling pathway that affects immune cell function. It is advised that test and treatment for latent TB be recommended before taking tofacitinib (Clunie et al. 2018, p. 702).

Biologic disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (bDMARDs)

bDMARDs or biologics are agents that are sub-classified into classes such as:

TNF- α blockers: TNF- α is a strong pro-inflammatory cytokine and levels are increased in auto-inflammatory and autoimmune inflammatory conditions. There are currently 5 main anti-TNF α bDMARDs available (Clunie et al. 2018, p. 703):

- **Adalimumab** - Humanised recombinant monoclonal antibody that binds to TNF- α receptor sites, most commonly used in moderate to severe RA (Harvey et al. 2009, p. 513)
- **Etanercept** - A recombinant human TNF α receptor fusion protein which acts as a decoy receptor
- **Certolizumab pegol** - A fragment of a monoclonal antibody specific to TNF- α which helps neutralise it (Kaushik and Moots 2005, p. 601-606)
- **Infliximab** - Chimeric monoclonal antibody which binds to TNF- α and neutralises it which prevents it from interacting with cell receptors
- **Golimumab** - A fully humanised recombinant anti-TNF α monoclonal antibody

B-cell depletion therapy: B lymphocytes are derived from bone marrow and are vital for the immune response, in RA B-cells perpetuate the inflammatory process in the synovium, this class of drugs deplete the B-cells and help reduce joint erosion and joint space narrowing:

- **Rituximab** - Genetically engineered chimeric monoclonal antibody which is directed against the CD20 antigen on the surface of normal and malignant B lymphocytes which causes B-cell depletion

Interleukin-6 (IL-6) inhibitors:

- **Tocilizumab** - A monoclonal antibody against the anti-IL-6 receptor, can also be used in conjunction with MTS in moderate to severe RA (Kumar and Clark 2021, p. 447).

Treatment Algorithm

The European Alliance of Associations for Rheumatology (formerly the European League Against Rheumatism) in 2010 developed recommendations for the management of RA with DMARDs. The algorithm is updated every 3 years and the last update was in 2022. According to the EULAR 2022 recommendations (Smolen et al. 2022, p. 7):

1. Therapy with DMARDs should be started as soon as the diagnosis of RA is made
2. Treatment should be aimed at reaching a target of sustained remission or low disease activity in every patient
3. Monitoring should be frequent in active disease (every 1–3 months); if there is no improvement by at most 3 months after the start of treatment or the target has not been reached by 6 months, therapy should be adjusted
4. MTX should be part of the first treatment strategy
5. In patients with a contraindication to MTX (or early intolerance), leflunomide or sulfasalazine should be considered as part of the (first) treatment strategy.
6. Short-term glucocorticoids should be considered when initiating or changing csDMARDs, in different dose regimens and routes of administration, but should be tapered and discontinued as rapidly as clinically feasible
7. If the treatment target is not achieved with the first csDMARD strategy, in the absence of poor prognostic factors, other csDMARDs should be considered
8. If the treatment target is not achieved with the first csDMARD strategy, when poor prognostic factors are present, a Efficacy: 1a; Efficacy: A; bDMARD should be added; JAK-inhibitors may be considered, but pertinent risk factors must be taken into account
9. bDMARDs and tsDMARDs should be combined with a csDMARD; in patients who cannot use csDMARDs as co-medication, IL-6 pathway inhibitors and tsDMARDs may have some advantages compared with other bDMARDs

10.If a bDMARD or tsDMARD has failed, treatment with another bDMARD or a tsDMARD should be considered; if one TNF or IL-6 receptor inhibitor therapy has failed, patients may receive an agent with another mode of action or a second TNF-/IL-6R-inhibitor

11.After glucocorticoids have been discontinued and a patient is in sustained remission, dose reduction of DMARDs (bDMARDs/tsDMARDs and/or csDMARDs) may be considered

(Figure 5) EULAR algorithm (Smolen et al. 2022, p. 8)

1. 2010 ACR-EULAR classification criteria can support early diagnosis.
 2. "Methotrexate should be part of the first treatment strategy". While combination therapy of csDMARDs is not preferred by the Task Force, starting with methotrexate does not exclude its use in combination with other csDMARDs although more adverse events without added benefit are to be expected, especially if MTX is combined with glucocorticoids.
 3. The treatment target is clinical remission according to ACR-EULAR definitions or, if remission is unlikely to be achievable, at least low disease activity; the target should be reached after 6 months, but therapy should be adjusted or changed if insufficient improvement (less than 50% of disease activity) is seen after 3 months.
 4. Sustained remission: ≥ 6 months ACR/EULAR index based or Boolean remission.
 5. Consider contraindications and risks. TNF-inhibitors (adalimumab, certolizumab, etanercept, golimumab, infliximab), including EMA/FDA approved tsDMARDs), abatacept, IL-6R inhibitors, or rituximab (under certain conditions), in patients who cannot use csDMARDs as concomitant IL-6-inhibitors and tsDMARDs have some advantages.
 6. The following risk factors for cardiovascular events and malignancies must be considered when intending to prescribe a JAK-inhibitor: Age over 65 years, history of current or past smoking, other cardiovascular risk factors (such as diabetes, obesity, hypertension), other risk factors for malignancy (current or previous history of malignancy other than successfully treated NMSC), risk factors for thromboembolic events (history of MI or heart failure, cancer, inherited blood clotting disorders or a history of blood clots, as well as patients taking combined hormonal contraceptives or hormone replacement therapy, undergoing major surgery or immobile).
 7. The most frequently used combination comprises methotrexate, sulfasalazine and hydroxychloroquine.
 8. Dose reduction or interval increase can be safely done with all bDMARDs and tsDMARDs with little risk of flares; stopping is associated with high flare rates; most but not all patients can recapture their good state upon re-institution of the same bDMARD/tsDMARD, but before all this glucocorticoids must have been discontinued.
 9. From a different or the same class.

2. Special Part

VIII. Aim:

- The aim of this study is to describe the therapeutic approach in rheumatoid arthritis with a focus on immunosuppressive therapies such as bDMARDs and tsDMARDs. Whether or not one therapy is more effective than the other, if there are patterns regarding therapy compared to sex as well as age of the patient.
- The specific objectives which will be included in the patient data analysis are as follows:
 - The number of csDMARDs and biologics used with specific data compared to popularity of use in various age ranges along with specific therapy types
 - The type of csDMARDs and biologics used and which is more prevalent (more effective) across age ranges and seropositivity rates
 - Types of biologics used with respect to first line and second line treatment and which is more prevalent
 - The use of monotherapy and combination therapy regarding both csDMARDs and biologics and any sufficient trends that lie within
 - The number of adverse effects regarding the drugs used and whether DMARDs are sufficiently safe to use in RA
 - The use of DMARDs and recent diagnosis of RA whether or not there is a correlation between age of disease and number of drugs used

IX. Methodology:

The study included a cohort of 40 patients admitted to the Rheumatology Clinic of the Emergency County Hospital in Craiova, Romania. Data collection was carried out from the clinic registry and individual patient files were selected from the clinic admissions during the 2022-2023 period. Case selection was based on an established diagnosis of rheumatoid arthritis and patient data was provided by medical history, imaging and laboratory clinical work-up.

This study is based on a retrospective analysis of the therapeutic recommendations in rheumatoid arthritis patients. Individual patient profiles included specific aspects of the

studied rheumatic pathology. Additionally, data regarding the therapeutic approach is included in the study, which includes use of csDMARDs, bDMARDs, and tsDMARDs, as well as the number of therapeutic agents used throughout the disease course.

Demographic profile and data regarding rheumatoid arthritis disease was retrieved for each patient, in the following manner:

- Sex
- Age
- History of disease
- Disease Activity Score 28 (CRP)
- Seropositivity
- Type of csDMARD used (MTX, LEF, HCQ, SSZ, or Ciclosporin)
- Type of biologic and targeted synthetic therapeutic class (TNF- α blocker, B cell therapy, IL-6 receptor inhibitor, or JAK inhibitor)
- Biologic and targeted synthetic DMARD used

Data regarding the treatment approach included the following aspects:

- Type of immunosuppressive therapy (DMARDs or biologics)
- Type of conventional synthetic csDMARDs used (MTX, LEF, HCQ, SSZ, or Ciclosporin)
- Type of biologic and synthetic therapeutic class (TNF blocker, B cell therapy, IL-6 receptor inhibitor, or JAK inhibitor)
- History of DMARD therapy
 - Number of prior conventional synthetic DMARDs
 - Number of prior biologic DMARDs
 - Adverse effects during therapy

The data regarding treatment approach and clinical profile was entered into a database using a spreadsheet editor similar to Microsoft Excel ('Numbers' a proprietary software developed by Apple Inc. as part of the iWork productivity suite for macOS Monterey version 12.6.7). Statistical data processing initially included a descriptive analysis of the study group according to demographic characteristics, seropositivity and clinical forms of the disease (Disease Activity Score 28), using the calculation functions: variance, range, mean, median, mode, and standard deviation. Subsequently, the study focused on the prevalence of drug classes used in the study group using comparative analysis as well as correlations with clinical features. Patients were analysed for the use of csDMARDs, biologic and targeted synthetic DMARDs, as well as adverse effects in the disease history. The graphical representation of the results were made by generating graphs in the form of pie charts and bar charts.

X. Results:

Figure 1

Analysis of study cohort by age (years)

Mean	62.225
Median	64
Mode	72
Standard Deviation	13.2752
Range	61
Minimum	22
Maximum	83

Figure 2

Figure 3

History of disease onset (year)

Mean	2010.45
Median	2011
Mode	2010, 2016, 2007
Standard Deviation	7.2251
Range	27
Minimum	1994
Maximum	2021

Figure 4

Disease Activity Score (DAS28-CRP)

Mean	4.5154
Median	4.72
Mode	5.5
Standard Deviation	1.3082
Variance	1.7114
Minimum	2.42
Maximum	7.17

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10

Figure 11

Figure 12

Figure 13

Figure 14

Figure 15

Figure 16

Figure 17

Figure 18

Figure 19

Analysis of TNF- α blocker by age (years)

Mean	62.5625
Median	63
Mode	72, 60
Range	32
Count	16
Minimum	43
Maximum	75

Figure 20

Analysis of IL-6 inhibitor by age (years)

Mean	70.6667
Median	72
Mode	72, 67, 73
Range	6
Count	3
Minimum	67
Maximum	73

Figure 21

Analysis of B cell Therapy by age (years)

Mean	62.75
Median	63
Mode	72, 58
Range	30
Count	8
Minimum	43
Maximum	73

Figure 22

Figure 23

Figure 24

Figure 25

Figure 26

Figure 27

Figure 28

Figure 29

Figure 30

Figure 31

Figure 32

XI. Discussion:

Data from the 40 patient cohort shows a 96% predominantly female distribution compared to only 4% of males in the study (Figure 1). This correlates with the research which states that RA predominantly affects females more than males (in some cases with a 3:1 ratio).

The mean of the cohort was 62 years with the median age being 64, the range spanning 61 years with the minimum age being 22 and the maximum being 83 (Figure 2). The population in this study has a mean age slightly older than what is seen in RA epidemiology studies, women have an increased incidence of RA until roughly the age of 50. According to this study RA tends to affect the elderly with those in the later decade of life affected the most (figure 3 with 34 patients out of 40 (85%) being above the 5th decade of life). Below the 5th decade of life the data shows only a 15% distribution of patients with RA, whilst it is not impossible to be diagnosed with RA during this age range it certainly shows a lower probability, at least regarding the sample size in this cohort.

History of onset of disease shows the mean year of onset is 2010 and the modal years being 2007, 2010, and 2016 (Figure 4). The age range is 27 years with the earliest diagnosis (at least based on seropositivity) being 1995 and the latest being 2021.

The DAS28 score data shows a mean score of 4.51 (moderate). The minimum score was 2.42 (low) and the maximum score was 7.17 (high) (Figure 5). In this cohort the largest number of patients scored moderate on the DAS28 scale with 17 patients (38%) and 13 patients (33%) scored high with only 8 patients (20%) scoring low (Figures 6 and 7). Only 4 patients (10%) showed no values or were incalculable due to insufficient data or errors in collecting data. Whilst 10% seems incredibly high when it comes to errors in collecting data one should keep in mind the size of the cohort, one way of mitigating this rate would be to increase the sample size and/or improving data collection and input once a patient has been diagnosed with strict adherence to protocol placed in mind.

The seropositivity rate in this cohort was 87.5%, with 12.5% being seronegative diagnosed with RA (Figure 8 and 9).

Figures 10 and 11 show an almost even spread between monotherapy with csDMARDs and combined therapy with csDMARDs and biologics/targeted synthetic DMARDs (55% and 45% respectively).

Figure 12 shows the percentage of csDMARDs used in this study, MTX is the highest at 38% with 30% of patients on LEF, 22% on HCQ, and 9% on SSZ with 1% being on Ciclosporin. This is in line with research and data which states that MTX is a first line drug for RA and most commonly prescribed.

csDMARD monotherapy shows only a 67.5% distribution in this cohort with 32.5% of patients on multiple csDMARDs according to figure 13.

Figure 14 shows the percentage of biologics used in the patient cohort with 65.7% using TNF- α blockers, 22.9% using B cell therapeutics, 8.6% using IL-6 inhibitors, and 2.9% using JAK inhibitors. Figure 30 also corroborates this in regard to the number of patients on each therapy class drug. Of the biologic agents used (Figures 15 and 16) etanercept was 32%, rituximab was 21%, adalimumab was 18%, certolizumab was 12%, tocilizumab 9%, and baricitinib/golimumab/tofacitinib each at 3%.

The number of prior csDMARDs used by the cohort (Figure 17) shows an overwhelming 50% of patients on 2 prior drugs. 25% were on 1 prior drug and 22.5% were on 3 prior drugs, with 2.5% being on 4. It seems to show that while patients on one, two, or three prior medications with csDMARDs are common; quad combination is relatively small possibly showing a reduced efficacy of combining that many drugs in therapy, most patients went through 1 or 2 prior csDMARDs which probably reflects the addition of biologics. Thus very few patients go through 3rd-line or 4th-line csDMARDs which could possibly be showing the efficacy of one and two prior drug therapy over all other prior drugs.

Figure 18 shows the number of prior biologics used in patients with 57.5% on no prior biologics, 17.5% on 2, 12.5% on 1 prior biologic, 7.5% on 3 prior and 5% on 4 prior drugs. This could be showing that the first bDMARDs were highly efficient in over half the patients (57.5% of patients on 0 prior biologics) where there is no need for more aggressive therapy and relying on biologics. It would seem that 1 or 2 prior biologics are the most common in this cohort. Continuing csDMARDs along with biologics may have had an added benefit in order to control the disease activity and thus avoid the need to switch to another biologic.

Adverse effects listed were only 25% in this cohort, compared to 75% reporting no adverse effects (Figure 19). Whilst no medication has zero adverse effects in all patients it seems that adverse effects in RA therapy are not as common according to these results. Corticosteroids can have toxic effects when administered above the therapeutic dose and also when stopping treatment. Withdrawing steroid therapy suddenly can lead to a flare-up of RA but more life-threatening is acute adrenal insufficiency resulting from an overly rapid withdrawal of corticosteroids after prolonged therapy. While some patients can recover from this in weeks or months, in some individuals the time to full recovery can be a year or longer. Prolonged therapy can cause fluid and electrolyte abnormalities, hypertension, hyperglycaemia, increased susceptibility to infection, peptic ulcers, osteoporosis, myopathy, behavioral disturbances, cataracts, growth arrest, and the characteristic habitus of steroid overdose, including fat redistribution, striae, and ecchymoses (Gilman, Alfred Goodman 2018, p. 853). When taking methotrexate the most common side effects are mucosal ulceration and nausea, with cytopenias (reduction in WBC count especially), cirrhosis of the liver, and an acute pneumonia-like syndrome may occur on chronic administration (Harvey et al. 2009, p. 511). Further side effects are

anaemia; decrease in appetite; diarrhoea; drowsiness; fatigue; gastrointestinal discomfort; headache; increased risk of infection; leucopenia; oral disorders; respiratory disorders; skin reactions; throat ulcer; thrombocytopenia; vomiting (Methotrexate | Drugs | BNF | NICE 2023). Leflunomide side effects are diarrhoea, neutropenia and/or thrombocytopenia, abnormal liver biochemistry, alopecia, and hypertension (Kumar and Clark 2021, p. 446). Sulfasalazine may cause leucopenia, pancytopenia, haemolysis, aplastic anaemia, and hepatic transaminitis, although bone marrow toxicity is unusual (Clunie et al. 2018, p. 294). TNF- α blockers share similar side effects to each other such as injection site reactions, heart failure, reversible lupus-like syndrome, infections, hypersensitivity reactions, or rarely — demyelination and autoimmune syndromes (Kumar and Clark 2021, p. 446).

The average age of those on TNF- α blockers (16 patients) is 62.56 with a range of 32 years. This shows a large spread in terms of age with those in the 6th decade of life and above being most common (Figure 20).

The average age of those on IL-6 inhibitors (3 patients) is 70.67 with a range of 6 years which points to this therapy being used in patients in the 7th decade of life, one could say this treatment is reserved as second line therapy and thus occurs in more elderly patients (Figure 21). Tocilizumab being the only IL-6 inhibitor used does come with precautions as well as side effects. Patients should be evaluated for tuberculosis before treatment. Patients and carers should be advised to seek immediate medical attention if symptoms of infection occur, or if symptoms of diverticular perforation such as abdominal pain, haemorrhage, or fever accompanying change in bowel habits occur (Tocilizumab | Drugs | BNF | NICE 2023). Further adverse effects are headache, skin eruption and stomatitis, fever, and anaphylactic reactions (Kumar and Clark 2021, p. 446). Cardiovascular disease is the main safety of concern in Anti-Interleukin-6 receptor inhibitors like Satralizumab and Tocilizumab as a result of an increase in cholesterol levels, but interleukin-6-receptor inhibitor therapy is safe and well-tolerated with an acceptable adverse effects profile (Kharel et al. 2021, p. 12). The elderly are more at risk for cardiovascular issues and therefore caution must be taken when prescribing in patients in the later decades of life. On a final note there have been instances of serious but rare risks of liver injury which require liver transplantation according to the MHRA in the UK: There have been reports of rare but serious cases of drug-induced liver injury, including acute liver failure and hepatitis, in patients treated with tocilizumab; some cases required liver transplantation. Serious liver injury was reported from 2 weeks to more than 5 years after initiation of tocilizumab. Healthcare professionals are advised to initiate tocilizumab treatment with caution in patients with active hepatic disease or hepatic impairment (Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency 2019).

The average age of those on B cell therapeutics (8 patients) is 62.75 with a range of 30 years which shows that this regimen can be used across a wide age gap regardless of decade of life, with the modal ages being 72 and 58 respectively (Figure 22).

Both TNF- α blockers and B cell therapeutics have an almost equal mean age at 62.56 and 62.75 years old respectively.

Seropositivity and use of DMARDs as shown in figure 24 tells us the number of patients being higher using csDMARDs and csDMARD/biologic combination at 18 and 16 patients respectively. Seronegative patients only had 5 patients on csDMARDs in monotherapy and 1 patient on combination.

Figure 25 shows the number of patients on csDMARD monotherapy and combination csDMARD/biologics with respect to sex. Naturally, when comparing with the data shown in figure 1, the number of female patients on both mono and combination therapy is higher, this does not show that males require fewer drugs, only that the data is heavily skewed to the female sex when it comes to RA especially in this cohort.

Figures 26 and 27 show DMARD use (both mono and combination therapy) within 5 years and 10 years history of the disease. Patients diagnosed over 5 years prior had more csDMARDs and csDMARDs/biologics (22 and 17 respectively) than those diagnosed within the last 5 years with RA. Comparing the data with patients diagnosed with RA over 10 years it would seem that combination therapy is higher than monotherapy (16 and 7 patients respectively). When looking at patients diagnosed with less than 10 years history of disease there is a higher number of csDMARD therapy, only patients at 16 compared to only 2 patients on combination therapy. The longer the disease history the higher the need to introduce biologic therapy. One could point out that under 5 years disease history there is little need for csDMARDs but when you go to 5-10 years monotherapy is more apparent. Once 10 years disease history is reached and surpassed monotherapy seems inefficient and combined therapy is required for treatment.

Taking a look at figure 28 we see the number of patients on bDMARDs and tsDMARDs, 17 patients and 2 patients. It is uncertain the reasons behind switching between bDMARDs and tsDMARDs, when comparing to other studies as they are not well documented. One could argue that the decision-making for b/tsDMARDs remains largely driven by clinical factors, but healthcare policy and safety concerns are also considered. Clinical reasons (such as strong overall efficacy, reduction of disease progression, reduction in joint stiffness etc) are cited by up to 97% of rheumatologists as the reason for switching to a bDMARD or tsDMARD, with only 68-76% being patient-centric reasons, and 53-63% being contraindication or safety reasons such as drug-drug interactions and others (Holdsworth et al. 2021, p. 2-6). Switching from TNF inhibitor bDMARD to third line treatment with

tsDMARD with 2/19 (10.5%) patients is in line with other studies where they switched from TNFi to JAKi with 12.5% of the patients switching (Holdsworth et al. 2021, p. 8).

First line treatment bDMARDs used (Figure 29) showed etanercept being the most popular at 7 patients and adalimumab with 6 patients being close behind as the drugs of favour in this cohort. In second line treatment we see rituximab being the most popular at 5 patients and etanercept with 4 patients.

Looking at figure 30 we see 17 patients on TNF- α blockers as the most common biologic used in this cohort, when comparing this with figure 14 above.

Figure 32 shows a higher use of DMARDs and biologics the further up in decade of life the age is. More patients above the 5th decade of life require multiple drugs, including combination therapy with csDMARDs and biologics. The 5th and 6th decade have an almost 50% distribution between monotherapy (csDMARDs only) and combination (csDMARDs and biologics), but this changes when reaching the 7th decade of life where there are more patients on csDMARD monotherapy than with combined therapy (9 versus 5). Precautions must be taken when treating elderly patients especially when considering treatment with TNF inhibitors and JAK inhibitors, heart failure is specific for TNF inhibitors and rituximab while risk of major adverse cardiac events and venous thromboembolism was listed for JAK inhibitors (Skaarup and Kragstrup 2022, p. 1). Patients on TNF inhibitor agents should not receive any live immunisations, and patients should be up to date with vaccinations before initiating them. Anti-TNF agents may be associated with a higher risk in patients undergoing major surgeries such as hip or knee replacement. The recommendation is to hold these medications one week and one dosing cycle before the surgery. They can be resumed two weeks after the surgery, provided there is no infection and incisions are healing well (Tumor Necrosis Factor Inhibitors - StatPearls - NCBI Bookshelf 2022)

According to the European Medicines Agency (the Pharmacovigilance Risk Assessment Committee) the review of available data from a clinical trial with JAK inhibitors confirmed that Tofacitinib increases the risk of major cardiovascular problems, cancer, VTE, serious infections, and death due to any cause when compared with TNF-alpha inhibitors (EMA recommends measures to minimise risk of serious side effects with Janus kinase inhibitors for chronic inflammatory disorders - European Medicines Agency 2022). According to the safety recommendations on JAK inhibitors issued in the EU; JAK inhibitors should be used only if no suitable treatment alternatives are available in patients aged 65 years or above, those at increased risk of major cardiovascular problems (such as heart attack or stroke), those who smoke or have done so for a long time in the past and those at increased risk of cancer (Safety Recommendation on Janus kinase (JAK) Inhibitors Issued in the European Union 2022). This data also corresponds with other safety studies from other sources stating that JAK inhibitors should not be prescribed for chronic inflammatory conditions in

people: with a history of cardiovascular disease (eg. heart attack or stroke), at increased risk of cardiovascular problems (eg. current or past long-time smokers), at increased risk of cancer, aged 65 years and over, unless there are no suitable alternative treatments available (Important safety information for Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitors 2023).

XII. Conclusions:

- Rheumatoid arthritis is a chronic systemic autoimmune disease of unknown aetiology which mainly targets smaller synovial joints, the proliferation of synovial tissues in the joint spaces causes bony destruction and joint space deformation. This leads to inflammation which further exacerbates the pain typically felt in the small joints of the hands and feet, although any synovial joint can be affected.
- Management of rheumatoid arthritis consists of pharmacological treatment in the form of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) for simple pain relief in mild RA, disease modifying anti-rheumatic drugs DMARDs (both synthetic and biologic) in mild, moderate, and severe cases; and surgical treatment in severe debilitating cases that aren't controllable by the aforementioned regimens.
- DMARDs can be classed into conventional synthetic (also called csDMARDs) or biologic (bDMARDs). csDMARDs include methotrexate, leflunomide, hydroxychloroquine, sulfasalazine, and ciclosporin among a few others. bDMARDs include, but are not limited to; adalimumab, baricitinib, certolizumab, etanercept, golimumab, rituximab, tocilizumab, and tofacitinib to name a few.
- The cohort of patients used in this study consisted mostly of female patients at 96% (which is in line with conventional data regarding RA diagnosis from other studies that show a higher female to male ratio and that women are more affected), 85% were above the 5th decade of life, 87.5% showing seropositivity (whilst seronegativity is by no means an indicator of being free of RA, seropositivity is still sufficient enough to use when diagnosing the condition), a mean age of 62 years, a mean DAS28 score of 4.5, and 75% showing no adverse effects regardless of whether csDMARDs or biologics were used.
- Treatment approach included csDMARDs and bDMARDs (biologic therapy), in both monotherapy and combined therapy (csDMARDs had 55% monotherapy in this cohort). This suggests that in almost half of patients csDMARD therapy is not sufficient to control disease activity and these cases require the addition of either a biologic or targeted synthetic therapy.
- Of the biologic drug classes used TNF- α showed a 65.7% majority with etanercept specifically being widely used amongst the group at 32%.
- Cases with seropositive RA recorded higher prevalence of combination therapy. One could infer that seropositivity is associated with a more active disease and worse prognosis.
- Whilst the percentage of adverse effects were only 25% in this cohort, all patients taking immunosuppressive therapy were regularly monitored and screened for adverse events according to well-established protocols.

References

1. Aletaha, D. et al., (2008). Reporting disease activity in clinical trials of patients with rheumatoid arthritis: EULAR/ACR collaborative recommendations. *Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases* [online]. 67(10), 1360–1364. [Viewed 14 April 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1136/ard.2008.091454
2. Arnett, F. C., Edworthy, S. M., Bloch, D. A., Mcshane, D. J., Fries, J. F., Cooper, N. S., Healey, L. A., Kaplan, S. R., Liang, M. H., Luthra, H. S., Medsger, T. A., Mitchell, D. M., Neustadt, D. H., Pinals, R. S., Schaller, J. G., Sharp, J. T., Wilder, R. L. and Hunder, G. G., (1988). The american rheumatism association 1987 revised criteria for the classification of rheumatoid arthritis. *Arthritis & Rheumatism* [online]. 31(3), 315–324. [Viewed 14 April 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1002/art.1780310302
3. Cava, A. L. and Albani, S., (1998). *Encyclopedia of Immunology* [online]. 2nd ed. Edited by Peter J. Delves. Elsevier. [Viewed 13 April 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1006/rwei.1999.0533
4. Clunie, G. P. R., Wilkinson, N., Nikiphorou, E. and Jadon, D., eds., (2018). *Oxford Handbook of Rheumatology* [online]. 4th ed. Oxford University Press. [Viewed 12 April 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1093/med/9780198728252.001.0001
5. Darby, M. J., Barron, D. A. and Hyland, R. E., eds., (2012). *Oxford Handbook of Medical Imaging* [online]. Oxford University Press. [Viewed 12 April 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1093/med/9780199216369.001.0001
6. de Pablo, P., Chapple, I. L. C., Buckley, C. D. and Dietrich, T., (2009). Periodontitis in systemic rheumatic diseases. *Nature Reviews Rheumatology* [online]. 5(4), 218–224. [Viewed 14 April 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1038/nrrheum.2009.28
7. EMA recommends measures to minimise risk of serious side effects with Janus kinase inhibitors for chronic inflammatory disorders - European Medicines Agency [online], (2022). European Medicines Agency. [Viewed 29 July 2023]. Available from:
8. Gilman, Alfred Goodman, (2018). *Goodman and Gilman's The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics*. 13th ed. Edited by Laurence L. Brunton, Randa Hilal-Dandan and Björn C. Knollmann. McGraw-Hill Education.
9. Greenmyer, J. R., Stacy, J. M., Sahmoun, A. E., Beal, J. R. and Diri, E., (2020). DAS28-CRP cutoffs for high disease activity and remission are lower than DAS28-ESR in rheumatoid arthritis. *ACR Open Rheumatology* [online]. 2(9), 507–511. [Viewed 5 July 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1002/acr2.11171

10. Harvey, R. A., Champe, P. C., Finkel, R., Cubeddu, L. X. and Clarke, M. A., eds., (2009). Lippincott's Illustrated Reviews: Pharmacology. 4th ed. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
11. Hazlewood, G. et al., (2011). Algorithm for identification of undifferentiated peripheral inflammatory arthritis: a multinational collaboration through the 3e initiative. *The Journal of Rheumatology Supplement* [online]. 87, 54–58. [Viewed 5 July 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.3899/jrheum.101076
12. Holdsworth, E. A., Donaghy, B., Fox, K. M., Desai, P., Collier, D. H. and Furst, D. E., (2021). Biologic and Targeted Synthetic DMARD Utilization in the United States: Adelphi Real World Disease Specific Programme for Rheumatoid Arthritis. *Rheumatology and Therapy* [online]. [Viewed 22 July 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1007/s40744-021-00357-1
13. Hou, W., Xu, G. and Wang, H., (2011). Treating autoimmune disease with chinese medicine [online]. Churchill Livingstone. [Viewed 13 April 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1016/b978-0-443-06974-1.x0001-2
14. Important safety information for Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitors [online], (2023). [Viewed 29 July 2023]. Available from:
15. Jameson, J. L., Fauci, A. S., Kasper, D. L., Hauser, S. L., Longo, D. L. and Loscalzo, J., (2018). *Harrison's Principles of Internal Medicine*. 20th ed. McGraw-Hill Education. Vol. 1.
16. Joint Formulary Committee, (2023). *British National Formulary*. 85th ed. Pharmaceutical Press.
17. Kaushik, V. and Moots, R., (2005). CDP-870 (certolizumab) in rheumatoid arthritis. *Expert Opinion on Biological Therapy* [online]. 5(4), 601–606. [Viewed 7 July 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1517/14712598.5.4.601
18. Kharel, S., Shrestha, S., Ojha, R., Guragain, N. and Ghimire, R., (2021). Safety and efficacy of interleukin-6-receptor inhibitors in the treatment of neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorders: a meta-analysis. *BMC Neurology* [online]. 21(1). [Viewed 23 July 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1186/s12883-021-02488-y
19. Kumar, P. J. and Clark, M. L., (2021). *Kumar & Clark's Clinical Medicine*. 10th ed. Elsevier.
20. Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency, (2019). Tocilizumab (RoActemra): rare risk of serious liver injury including cases requiring transplantation [online]. GOV.UK. [Viewed 24 July 2023]. Available from:

21. Methotrexate | Drugs | BNF | NICE [online], (2023). NICE. [Viewed 24 July 2023]. Available from:
22. NEGREI, C., BOJINCA, V., BALANESCU, A., BOJINCA, M., BACONI, D., SPANDIDOS, D. A., TSATSAKIS, A. M. and STAN, M., (2016). Management of rheumatoid arthritis: Impact and risks of various therapeutic approaches. *Experimental and Therapeutic Medicine* [online]. 11(4), 1177–1183. [Viewed 23 July 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.3892/etm.2016.3045
23. Nishimura, K., Sugiyama, D., Kogata, Y., Tsuji, G., Nakazawa, T., Kawano, S., Saigo, K., Morinobu, A., Koshiba, M., Kuntz, K. M., Kamae, I. and Kumagai, S., (2007). Meta-analysis: diagnostic accuracy of anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide antibody and rheumatoid factor for rheumatoid arthritis. *Annals of Internal Medicine* [online]. 146(11), 797. [Viewed 13 April 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.7326/0003-4819-146-11-200706050-00008
24. O'Dell, J., Moore, G., Mikuls, T., Cannella, A. and Erikson, A., (2013). *Rheumatology: A Color Handbook*. Manson Publishing Ltd.
25. Prevoo, M. L. L., Van'T Hof, M. A., Kuper, H. H., Van Leeuwen, M. A., Van De Putte, L. B. A. and Van Riel, P. L. C. M., (1995). Modified disease activity scores that include twenty-eight-joint counts development and validation in a prospective longitudinal study of patients with rheumatoid arthritis. *Arthritis & Rheumatism* [online]. 38(1), 44–48. [Viewed 14 April 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1002/art.1780380107
26. Provan, D., ed., (2018). *Oxford Handbook of Clinical and Laboratory Investigation* [online]. 4th ed. Oxford University Press. [Viewed 12 April 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1093/med/9780198766537.001.0001
27. Rang, H. P., Dale, M. M., Ritter, J. M., Flower, R. J. and Henderson, G., (2012). *Rang and Dale's Pharmacology*. 7th ed. Churchill Livingstone.
28. Safety Recommendation on Janus kinase (JAK) Inhibitors Issued in the European Union [online], (2022). [Viewed 29 July 2023]. Available from:
29. Skaarup, L. and Kragstrup, T. W., (2022). AB1428 CONTRAINDICATIONS, BOXED WARNINGS AND SPECIAL WARNINGS OF BIOLOGICAL AND TARGETED SYNTHETIC DMARDS. *Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases* [online]. 81(Suppl 1), 1820.2–1820. [Viewed 23 July 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1136/annrheumdis-2022-eular.760
30. Smolen, J. S. et al., (2022). EULAR recommendations for the management of rheumatoid arthritis with synthetic and biological disease-modifying antirheumatic

- drugs: 2022 update. *Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases* [online]. ard—2022–223356. [Viewed 9 July 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1136/ard-2022-223356
31. Tocilizumab | Drugs | BNF | NICE [online], (2023). NICE. [Viewed 24 July 2023]. Available from:
 32. Tumor Necrosis Factor Inhibitors - StatPearls - NCBI Bookshelf [online], (2022). National Center for Biotechnology Information. [Viewed 29 July 2023]. Available from:
 33. Watts, R. A., Conaghan, P. G., Denton, C., Foster, H., Isaacs, J. and Müller-Ladner, U., eds., (2013). *Oxford Textbook of Rheumatology* [online]. 4th ed. Oxford University Press. [Viewed 12 April 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1093/med/9780199642489.001.0001
 34. Wilkinson, I. B., Raine, T., Wiles, K., Goodheart, A., Hall, C. and O'Neill, H., (2017). *Oxford Handbook of Clinical Medicine* [online]. 10th ed. Oxford University Press. [Viewed 12 April 2023]. Available from: doi: 10.1093/med/9780199609628.001.0001